

Blue Transitions in the Black Sea: Living Labs as a tool to support the transition to a sustainable blue economy in the Black Sea

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Abstract

This paper captures an ongoing joint initiative which spans three EU-funded projects active within the Black Sea region, each utilising living labs to support the overall development of the Blue Economy in a sustainable manner. The Black Sea is a complex resource-rich socio-ecological ecosystem nestled within a dynamic geo-political space, thus providing both fundamental challenges and great opportunities within the Blue Economy sectors. Each of the projects adopts diverse yet complimentary foci in terms of stakeholder groups, geographic location, thematic focus and level of governance. The paper outlines the overarching methodology of Systems Innovation for Blue Transition implemented by the initiative, before presenting each project and the activities undertaken therein. The paper concludes on the potential implications held by emerging findings, both methodological and thematic, on the sustainable development of the Blue Economy and related policy in the region.

Key words

Living Labs, Co-creation, Blue Economy, Black Sea, Systems Approaches

Introduction

The Blue Economy represents the overall contribution of seas, oceans and other marine or aquatic ecosystems to a nation or a region's wealth. The EU's Blue Economy is recognized as a major driver for development within Europe, and is clearly identified as a priority area for growth [1]. At the same time, European seas are overexploited, being placed under multiple pressures from human activities [2], this has led the European Commission to acknowledge the need to transition toward a sustainable Blue Economy [3]. This can only be achieved through the preservation of marine ecosystem services and their resilience towards the multiple anthropogenic stressors.

Figure 1. Map of the Black Sea

Located in south-eastern Europe, on the outer limits of the EU, the region is regarded as a 'strategic bridge', an economic, geopolitical and trade corridor of strategic importance, connecting to the Mediterranean Sea, and Europe with Asia and the Middle East. It is a dynamic, heterogeneous region characterized by the countries' great economic potential, diverging interests [4] but also an open conflict. That said, the Blue Economy within the region is still largely under-developed [4], with vast reserves of untapped potential for economic development. Its significance for the development of the region was formally recognized by the key regional actors in the Burgas Vision paper [5] and the Common Maritime Agenda [6]. The Black Sea itself, despite being resource-rich, also exemplifies the current poor environmental status of European Seas, and is widely regarded as one of the most polluted seas on the globe. The poor water quality has had a significant impact on fish populations, and the diversity of species is gravely threatened. The negative environmental effects of the poor ecological status inevitably

harbour socio-economic consequences on employment, food security, tourism and health; thereby calling for an urgent transition towards a more sustainable development trajectory within the Blue Economy.

Through 3 different EU Horizon funded projects, Living Labs (LLs) are being implemented to support this transition, bringing stakeholders at the core of the strategy. This current research-in-progress paper seeks to share with the Living Lab community insights from the current experiments on 1) how LLs are used in the context of the “blue transition” 2) how a system innovation approach has been implemented to trigger transformative processes, 3) how collaboration across EU projects strengthen stakeholder engagement impacts.

Methodology

A System Innovation Approach for Blue transition

The System Innovation Approach (SIA) is a methodological framework which enables systemic change based on an interconnected set of innovations, where each influences the other; with innovation both in the parts of the system and in the ways in which they interconnect. SIA is rooted in system thinking [7], and its implementation within the context of the research draws on transition management [8;9] in order to deal with persistent problems and facilitate sustainability. It is based on a highly participatory methodology where stakeholders are actively engaged in LLs, resulting in the co-identification of an interconnected set of innovations to drive the desired transition. In this context, LLs act as open innovation spaces which foster co-creation with users, the end result is expected to better solve stakeholder needs. Stakeholders are engaged, from many different domains and scale-levels, in solving problems oriented activities, co-production of knowledge and co-design of solutions in an iterative process [10;11]. They are actively involved in co-identifying main challenges and needs related to the Blue Economy in the Black Sea, co-defining common goals in a form of a desirable future vision. Envisioning desirable futures is a critical step toward creating a sustainable future [12]; it gives a sense of direction to enable positive transformation [13;14]; finally, pathways can be co-developed to drive the region towards a sustainable state.

Towards a complementary stakeholder strategy across EU projects Black Sea stakeholders from the quadruple helix are currently engaged through 3 different projects which allow the involvement of multi-level stakeholder (local, national and regional) while covering different facet of the problem (figure 2).

The BRIDGE-BS project objective is to advance the Black Sea’s marine research and

innovation to co-develop Blue Economy pathways under multi-stressors for the sustainable utilization of the ecosystem services. Five LLs covering the Romanian, Bulgarian and Georgian Black Sea coastline and marine space as well as two Turkish regions (Istanbul/Bosporus and Sinup) are being implemented. In the BRIDGE_BS context, LLs represent an instrument to empower local communities in the future sustainable management of the Black Sea, breaking sectoral silos and ensuring a systemic approach. They create a new local participative dynamic to explore alternative forms of governance while being a focal point for greater interconnection between physical and socio-economic sciences. Various participative tools exploit and enhance the inter-actor exchanges, to create a learning loop, raise awareness on ecosystem services and their multi-stressors, current and future, stimulate a thinking “out of the box”, develop trust and collaborations, to foster the adoption and implementation of innovative eco-solutions. The main outputs will be transformative pathways for a sustainable Blue Economy for each country.

Figure 2. The overarching framework for the interactions between the three projects

The BRIDGE-BS sister project, DOORS will link citizens, science, and industry for the vital regeneration of the Black Sea, stimulating a new wave of 'Blue Economy' opportunities through the development of a System of System to address the human and climate change impacts on the marine ecosystem. Stakeholder engagement determines DOORS' success, value, and impacts. They drive science and technology breakthroughs with researchers, making the project work more meaningful on the ground. Here Multi-Actor Forums (MAFs) are implemented, as a different form of

stakeholder engagement structure, which bring together national stakeholders in the same countries as the BRIDGE-BS LLs, from all backgrounds, to help scientists prioritizing Black Sea issues with a focus on Blue Economy policies and the use of innovations to fill identified gaps.

Finally, the ARSINOE project aims at building an ecosystem for climate change adaptation solutions, it does not focus on the Black Sea specifically but has a dedicated Black Sea case study covering the Danube Delta in Romania, the Ropotami river in Bulgaria and the Bosphorus region in Turkey, looking at land-sea interactions from source-to-sea in the context of climate change. Stakeholders from each region are engaged in what is called national working groups (WG) which are then feeding the discussion occurring in an international LLs where representatives from regional institutions and national WG are brought together to tackle the identified problems and envisage solutions in a regional perspective.

Spaces for Change: Engaging Stakeholders via a coordinated set of Living Labs

The first round of local BRIDGE-BS LLs has involved more than 120 stakeholders in 8 workshops representing all Blue Economy sectors. The workshops were divided into four active participatory activities in order to identify 1) key Black Sea ecosystem services from the perception of local stakeholders 2) pressures and risks related to ecosystem services, 3) local challenges and needs for the sustainable development of the region, and finally 4) Blue Economy opportunities. The results allowed drawing a comprehensive understanding of the system, key drivers and issues to tackle to transition towards a sustainable Economy in the region. Findings from the different local LLs turned out to be very similar across countries calling for a coordinated Blue Economy strategy across the region. Within a second round of workshops, local stakeholders in each LL co-developed a common vision for their region while the third workshop will dive into transformative processes to support the transition toward sustainability.

In parallel, at national level, four MAF workshops were conducted where academic, industrial, regional government delegates shared their perspectives on Black Sea socioeconomic and policy needs for the emergence of a sustainable Blue Economy. An online survey was also launched to determine the Blue Economy obstacles and potential in the region, inquiring about the development of Blue Economy sectors and entrepreneurial support, obstacles, and priorities. This first phase of stakeholders' interactions prioritized the Blue Economy sectors based on the national context, to then

map national needs and opportunities. The resulted analysis will highlight policy gaps between national Black Sea Blue Economy needs, and EU strategic and policy priorities, and potential discrepancies with local realities (BRIDGE-BS LL outputs).

Two online international workshops took also place so far. Following a mapping of key land-sea interactions, integrating the outputs of national workshops in Romania, Bulgaria and Turkey, data collection and monitoring were identified as key priority issues across the region when it comes to fresh and marine water management and climate change which became the focus of this international LL.

Conclusions and next steps

The development of the Blue Economy within the Black Sea is at a crucial juncture, where strong foundations must be laid to ensure the that burgeoning Blue Economy in the region evolves and transitions in a direction that is in harmony with sustainability and resilience. Different type of LLs have been implemented across the region to support the transition towards sustainability; local, national, and regional stakeholder representatives are being engaged in solving problems oriented activities, co-production of knowledge and co-design of solutions. The use of a system innovation approach combining system thinking and transition management methodology allowed so far to a better understanding of complex Black Sea systems from science-society perspectives in an iterative, interactive and reflexive ways, and setting up priority issues. It will enable the co-development of complementary pathways based on the co-identification of a portfolio of innovations and actions to support the necessary blue transition.

A comparative analysis of the initial outputs of the BRIDGE-BS local LLs and DOORS national MAFs will allow to assess whether local and national needs and priorities aligned and flag out to national policy makers’ potential miss-matched. The national innovation pathways to be developed by the DOORS MAFs in order to fill existing regional blue policy gaps will serve as a basis for the co-development of the BRIDGE-BS transformative pathways which aim at providing a roadmap for change in order to reach the sustainable future co-designed by local stakeholders in each country. The ARSINOE international LL provide the fora for sharing experience and knowledge across countries.

Moreover, the framing of a joint stakeholder engagement strategy across multiple European projects is facilitating collaboration and sharing of experiences of running LLs across research teams, contributing to the development of a strong interdisciplinary cross-country marine research community in the Black Sea. It also provides a better visibility to local practitioners on the overall purpose and progresses of the Living Labs initiatives as well as their specific contributions.

References

1. European Commission, 2012, Coastal and Maritime Tourism, <https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/sector-information/coastal-and-maritime-tourism>, European Commission,
2. EEA, 2019, Marine messages II: Navigating the course towards clean, healthy and productive seas through implementation of an ecosystem-based approach, EEA Report , No 17/2019, European Environment Agency,
3. EC, 2021, new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future, COM/2021/240 final, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:240:FIN>
4. European Commission, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, Joint Research Centre, Addamo, A., Calvo Santos, A., Guillén, J., et al., 2022, The EU blue economy report 2022, Publications Office of the European Union, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/793264>
5. Burgas Vision paper (VP), 2018: https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/maritimeday/sites/mare-emd/files/burgas-visionpaper_en.pdf
6. Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea (CMA), 2019, <http://www.bsec-bsvkc.org/UploadedDocuments/Ministerial%20Declaration%20on%20the%20COMMON%20MARITIME%20AGENDA%20FOR%20THE%20BLACK%20SEA.pdf>
7. Meadows, Donella H., 2008, "Thinking in Systems: A Primer." Chelsea Green: White River.
8. Roorda, C., uliaWitt Mayer J. ,Henneman P., van Steenbergen F, Frantzeskaki N, Loorbach D., 2014, "Transition management in the urban context: guidance manual." DRIFT, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Rotterdam
9. Loorbach, Derk A. and Rotmans J., 2007, "Managing transitions for sustainable development."
10. Geels F. W., Schot J.,2007, "Typology of sociotechnical transition pathways." Research Policy, no 36, (2007) 399–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2007.01.003>
11. Roorda, C., Akinsete E., 2013, "MUSIC Aberdeen, "Mini Guide to Transition Management" Rotterdam: Dutch Research Institute For Transitions
12. Bennett, Elena M., Reinette Biggs, Garry D. Peterson and Gordon, Line J., 2021, "Patchwork Earth: navigating pathways to just, thriving, and sustainable futures." One Earth, no 4, 172–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.01.004>
13. Milkoreit, Manjana. "Imaginary politics: Climate change and making the future. Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene, 5(62) (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1525/journal.elementa.254>
14. Riedy, Chris,Sandra Waddock. "Imagining transformation: Change agent narratives of sustainable futures." Futures, no 142 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2022.103010>.

